

THE MARITIME BORDER AGREEMENT BETWEEN LEBANON AND ISRAEL AND THE ENERGY DYNAMICS IN THE EASTERN MEDITERRANEAN

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ABSTRACT

On October 27th, 2022, Lebanon and Israel reached an understanding regarding their disputed maritime borders. The agreement, brokered by the United States of America, has been treated as "historic" by most media outlets because its initiative as an economic dialogue between two warring countries without the prior need for a peace settlement. The new division of the maritime area into two mutually agreed Exclusive Economic Zones unveiled new opportunities for oil and natural gas exploration in the Eastern Mediterranean region. Hence, the Levantine Basin gained notoriety not only for the potential of its reserves, but also due to the geopolitical moment of energy scarcity that most of the adjacent states are going through. Noting the sharp inflation of the Lebanese economy since 2015, the Russian-Ukrainian conflict since early 2022, the Israeli political instability since 2017, and the strategic repositioning of the United States after the resurgence of the Taliban in 2021, the energy issue has become a priority for these countries seeking to survive a politically and economically troubled global conjuncture.

Despite the optimism of states and oil companies, the current international context did not seem to favor an understanding along the lines of the Lebanese-Israeli one. For that matter, the agreement still has weaknesses and institutional loopholes that could rapidly shorten its validity. At the same time, despite the reductionist analyses that condemn the region to be a constant breeding ground for conflict, the agreement has enabled an equally unexpected degree of satisfaction and compliance between both Israeli and Lebanese authorities on economic issues of common interest. As such, its nature and prospects are still uncertain and dependent on a myriad of yet unknown behavioral variables. However, there is a conjuncture that explains why this agreement was possible, even against trends and anticipations.

BACKGROUND

Lebanon and Israel have had a history of conflict for approximately a century, with two belligerent moments standing out: the Lebanese Civil War (1975-1990) and the July War (2006). The international community's major effort for the cessation of hostilities culminated in the creation of the United Nations Interim Force in Lebanon (UNIFIL), still active. Despite this peacekeeping operation, political frictions and occasional conflicts persist between the countries, especially in the border regionⁱⁱ. In aggravation,

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Hizbullah - a Lebanese political party and militant group - has relations of political and military cooperation with Shiite organizations throughout the Arab World, in addition to Iran itself, Israel's declared regional rival (1a, 1b).

The regional geopolitical scenario was apparently adverse for an understanding on maritime boundaries and offshore hydrocarbon exploration between the countries. Despite this, on October 27th, 2022, both countries agreed on a sharing project brokered by the United States of America. Under the agreementⁱⁱⁱ, oil and natural gas exploration rights in the Eastern Mediterranean region (see Appendix, Map 1) were delimited by the Line 23 (see Appendix, Map 2). Large media outlets have been optimistically referring to the agreement as "historic", given that it is the first diplomatic communication between the countries - albeit indirectly - since the Arab-Israeli War (1948). Amid this understanding, the attraction of investments and companies interested in energy prospecting to the region have underpinned the mutual trust between the countries.

Since 2020, Lebanon and Israel have been negotiating the allotment of subsoil resources discovered in the 2000s. In the current demarcation conditions, Israel now has exploration rights south of Line 23, particularly over the Karish field, while Lebanon has the areas north of this border, mainly the Qana field. The assignment of the prospecting companies was also defined in parallel, but simultaneously, with the negotiations: the Greek company Energean is responsible for the Israeli reserves, and the French Total for the Lebanese reserves. In terms of energy geopolitics, the current conjuncture may have influenced the understanding between the countries: Lebanon undergoes domestic political unrest amid a severe inflationary crisis; Europe suffers from natural gas shortages as a result of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict; the United States experiences a redefinition of its strategic priorities following the resurgence of tensions in the South China Sea and the Taliban's retaking of power in Afghanistan; and Israel elects its fifth prime minister in a four-year period amid political stalemates in the Knesset^{iv}.

FINDINGS

The agreement on maritime borders between Lebanon and Israel has an arguable legal nature, since it represents a specific agreement on an economic issue that did not require a prior peace agreement between the countries - which, formally, are still in conflict. Nor is there any way to approximate this achievement to a cooperation between the countries, given that both have separately signed their commitment to the United States. The sharing of the Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs)^v in the Eastern Mediterranean, drawing on a brief moment of armistice, does not extend to an agreement on land borders - the major driving force for Lebanese-Israeli belligerence. In this sense, the very enclosure of Line 23 between the maritime zones of Haifa (Israel) and Naqoura (Lebanon) crosses, on the continent, the demilitarization zone established between the countries by UNIFIL in 2000, known as the Blue Line^{vi}.

The one-off understanding between the governments of Tel Aviv and Beirut does not mean an appeasement of tensions between Israel and Hizbullah. The organization, which has a paramilitary

capability said to be larger than the Lebanese Armed Forces itself (2a, 2b), remains dissatisfied with the terms of the agreement. Hezbollah, which also had three drones shot down in July by the Israel Defense Forces flying over the Karish camp^{vii}, alleges usurpation of the Lebanese right to exploit its own wealth^{viii} and subservience of the government to US interests^{ix}. On the Israeli side, Prime Minister-elect Benjamin Netanyahu^x questioned the legitimacy of then incumbent Yair Lapid^{xi} to ratify the agreement, claiming it was an interim mandate^{xii} and endorsed his intention to neutralize the agreement^{xiii}.

In addition to the remaining tensions between Israel and Hezbollah, recent disagreements between the Mediterranean countries in terms of energy policy make the viability of such an agreement hardly sustainable in the long term. Since the beginning of the conflict in Ukraine, European imports of Russian natural gas have fallen by about 70% compared to 2021, a fact that has driven a diversification of suppliers (mainly Norway, Algeria and the United States)^{xiv} accompanied by sharp inflation^{xv}. In this vein, the potential for hydrocarbon exploration in the Eastern Mediterranean can be seen as a European alternative to dependence on Russia. Despite this, there are still no efficient ways of transporting natural gas in large quantities from the Middle East to Europe. According to Mathios Rigas^{xvi}, Energean's CEO, the main alternatives to circumvent this logistical problem would be: a) increasing the flow of gas liquefaction tankers in the region, which would require more maritime safety and security infrastructures; b) creating a pipeline to the liquefaction station in Cyprus, which would be a long-term plan; and c) resuming the construction of the Eastern Mediterranean Gas Pipeline (EastMed), which was halted in January 2022.

CONCLUSIONS

The maritime border agreement between Lebanon and Israel, in terms of international law, represents a partial and isolated advance in terms of allowing a dialogue between belligerent nations. In economic terms, it provides a workable alternative to the supply of natural gas to Europe, as well as attracting investments in the offshore prospecting in the Eastern Mediterranean region. However, beyond the Lebanese and Israeli discontents, the extra-regional scenario is far from being conducive to a cooperative approach in terms of energy. This animosity can be traced back to the interruption of the EastMed project and its relation to the high pace of the agreement itself.

Stemming from a Project of Common Interest^{xvii}, EastMed was appointed by European Council Regulation 347/2013^{xviii} to diversify commercial partnerships in oil and gas. It concerns the project of a pipeline connecting the Levantine Basin's fields to Cyprus, then to Greece and Italy. Designed to flow about 10 billion m³ per year, the nearly 2,000-kilometer-long pipeline was scheduled to be delivered by 2027, built in a partnership between the Italian Edison and Greek DEPA^{xix} companies. As a maritime connection between Israel and Europe, the EastMed was intended to enter the continent in two ways: via the Italian "Poseidon" pipeline, and through the Greece-Bulgaria Gas Interconnector (see Appendix, maps 3 and 4). In January 2022, the United States withdrew its support for EastMed claiming it was an economically unfeasible and environmentally unsustainable project^{xx}. Difficulties in settling a new

source of funding led to a project re-evaluation, for which around \$40 million dollars has already been invested^{xxi}. Meanwhile, Turkey raised initial regrets about the proposal, alleging it was excluded from its further implementation^{xxii}. As a result, the country bilaterally signed a memorandum of understanding^{xxiii} with Libya on the delimitation of a common EEZ, as well as their maritime jurisdiction, causing friction with adjacent countries^{xxiv} - as an example, an agreement along the same lines between Greece and Egypt^{xxv} can be mentioned as a response to this Turkish initiative. The EastMed project currently remains of interest to Palestine, Cyprus, France, Greece, Italy, Israel, Jordan, and Egypt, although some unease about its existence persists.

Despite the antagonisms, there are reasons to consider a resumption of cooperative energy arrangements in the Mediterranean after the maritime agreement between Lebanon and Israel. Noteworthy among them is the successful drilling of the Karish field by Energean, which reported a 13 billion m³ natural gas field^{xxvi} discovery in the so-called Olympus Area by the end of October 2022^{xxvii} (see Appendix, map 5). Energean thus plays an important role in the future of the agreement as it establishes an economic communication between the two countries and the European demands for these seabed resources. The company, which has been prospecting offshore in Israel since 2014, also intends to drill in Tamar, Lebanon^{xxviii}, and in the Gaza Marine basin, Palestine^{xxix}, potentially generating an influx of capital to the region and, consequently, positive economic outcomes for the countries involved. Furthermore, Energean's partnership with Italy's Edison, along with granting access to drilling zones in Egypt, Algeria, Italy, and Croatia, could be a trigger for the renewal of negotiations regarding the future of EastMed and its relationship to the terms of the Lebanese-Israeli agreement.

SUGGESTIONS

The maritime agreement between Lebanon and Israel, despite its potential to engender greater understanding regarding the sharing and use of maritime zones in the Mediterranean, has complex political and situational constraints. Therefore, there is no way to foresee unequivocally the maintenance, deepening or even the abandonment of the agreements' conditions in the short, medium, or long term. Any situational analysis must move away from simplistic economic optimism, which sees a one-time agreement as the beginning of regional peace, as well as from fatalistic pessimism, which reduces the region to a cyclical breeding ground of conflict over territory and resources. The possibility of exploring subsoil in the Levantine Basin brings both solutions for intra- and extra-regional energy demands, but also concerns about this resource's exploitation and its resulting wealth distribution. In addition to these economic obstacles, the terms of the agreement have provoked domestic countermoves in both Lebanon and Israel, which have had their territorial claims insufficiently met in the long-standing dispute over the maritime border.

The main concern for the decision-makers must be, amidst the uncertainties, not letting the disagreements in both countries stretch to the level of conflict. To do so, an equitable co-participation of prospecting royalties is needed, which takes into consideration not only Israeli financial and structural

investments, but also Lebanese weaknesses amidst rising inflation and energy shortages. Insofar as social inequality is pointed out as a notable conflict generator, it is not uncommon to imagine that paramilitary entities and non-state organizations on both sides may resort to violence as a demonstration of dissatisfaction if the agreement's benefits are not satisfactory. Thus, the historical interconnection between the Mediterranean and Middle Eastern countries demonstrates that national instabilities can often extend beyond their territories. As Europe is momentarily weakened by the consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian conflict, the international community's (especially the European Union and the North Atlantic Treaty Organization) ability to act in containing insurgencies is notably limited. Therefore, the prospecting companies involved in this process, as central actors in the agreement's success or failure, even though they are private capital entities - and, as such, wish to optimize their investment returns - cannot disregard sustainability (especially in its social aspect) in their planning.

As US brokering made possible the settlement terms between Lebanon and Israel, a multilateral architecture must be considered to provide it with greater legitimacy and institutional robustness under international law. This suggests that the specific agreements reached on the maritime borders can be used to some extent for the countries' continental frontiers. Such reasoning, albeit a mere horizon, can help easing the sources of vindictiveness between countries that, armistice after armistice, remain the main reasons for conflict resumptions.

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APPENDIX

Map 1: Disputed Exclusive Economic Zone frontiers before agreement signature (in dark blue) and location of hydrocarbons submarine basins (in red).

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Map 2: Location of Qana and Karish gas fields in the disputed Exclusive Economic Zone prior to the signing of the agreement. Boundary claimed by Israel (line 1); boundary claimed by Lebanon (line 29); previous unaccepted agreement proposal (line H); and boundary established by the agreement (line 23).

Retrieved from: OSSEIRAN, Hashem (October 6th, 2022). Lebanon years away from gas riches even if it closes border deal with Israel. Available at: <<https://www.timesofisrael.com/lebanon-years-away-from-gas-riches-even-if-it-closes-border-deal-with-israel/>>. Accessed December 2022.

Map 3: East Mediterranean Pipeline (EastMed) original design showing its connection from Levantine Basin (dashed line) to the Poseidon pipeline and to the Gas Interconnector Greece-Bulgaria (IGB).

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Map 4: Position of the Qana, Karish and Leviathan oil and gas fields (in red) relative to the Eastern Mediterranean Pipeline project (in yellow).

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Map 5: Olympus Area inside Israel's Exclusive Economic Zone. In red, new prospecting zones discovered by Energean after the agreement was signed. In green, already known drilling zones.

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ⁱⁱ Available at: <<https://www.atlanticcouncil.org/blogs/menasource/lebanon-and-israel-blue-line-tensions/>>. Accessed December 2022.

ⁱⁱⁱ Available at: <<https://www.haaretz.com/israel-news/2022-10-12/ty-article/full-text-final-version-of-israel-lebanon-maritime-border-deal/00000183-cb43-d8cc-afc7-ffef25f80000>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{iv} Knesset (Hebrew for "meeting") is the unicameral assembly that holds Israel's legislative power, consisting of 120 parliamentary chairs.

^v UNCLOS/1982, art. 55: "The exclusive economic zone is an area beyond and adjacent to the territorial sea, subject to the specific legal regime established in this Part, under which the rights and jurisdiction of the coastal State and

the rights and freedoms of other States are governed by the relevant provisions of this Convention". UNCLOS/1982, art. 57: "The exclusive economic zone shall not extend beyond 200 nautical miles from the baselines from which the breadth of the territorial sea is measured".

^{vi} Available at: <<https://unifil.unmissions.org/it%E2%80%99s-time-talk-about-blue-line-constructive-re-engagement-key-stability>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{vii} Available at: <<https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2022/7/2/israel-shoots-down-unarmed-hezbollah-drones>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{viii} Available at: <<https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20221012-hezbollah-to-remain-vigilant-amid-israel-lebanon-maritime-border-deal/>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{ix} Available at: <<https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20221112-nasrallah-we-want-president-that-is-not-submissive-to-us/>>. Accessed December 2022.

^x Netanyahu was Prime Minister of Israel from 2009 to 2021 and was re-elected for 2023. At the time the agreement was signed, he headed the opposition caucus in the Knesset for Likud, the party he has been leader since 2005.

^{xi} Lapid was officially sworn in as Prime Minister of Israel in July 2022, after about a year as interim prime minister. Additionally, he has served as Foreign Minister since June 2021. He founded his current party, Yesh Atid (Hebrew for "there is a future"), in 2012 and was appointed Finance Minister the following year by Benjamin Netanyahu, which he left in 2014.

^{xii} Available at: <<https://www.timesofisrael.com/netanyahu-lapid-is-giving-away-sovereign-territory-to-hezbollah-in-maritime-deal/>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xiii} Available at: <<https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/netanyahu-pledges-neutralize-lebanon-maritime-deal>>. Accessed December 2022.

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^{xvi} Available at: <<https://en.globes.co.il/en/article-energean-ceo-were-looking-at-new-drilling-near-tamar-1001416136>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xvii} Projects of Common Interest are "large infrastructures that connect energy grids across Europe and boost the use of renewable energy, ensuring that secure, clean and affordable energy reaches all citizens". European Commission (November 24th, 2017). What are the Projects of Common Interest? How do they improve and modernize Europe's energy grid? Available at: <<https://audiovisual.ec.europa.eu/en/video/l-147329>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xviii} Available at: <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2013:115:0039:0075:en:PDF>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xix} Free translation from Greek: Public Gas Corporation of Greece.

^{xx} Available at: <<https://www.politico.eu/article/eastmed-a-pipeline-project-that-ran-afoul-of-geopolitics-and-green-policies/>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxi} Available at: <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2013/347/oj/eng>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxii} Available at: <<https://thearabweekly.com/eastmed-pipeline-project-fend-turkish-hegemony-bid>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxiii} Available at: <<https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2019-12-05/turkey-s-parliament-backs-contentious-maritime-deal-with-libya>>. Accessed December 2022. The memorandum was canceled by the Al-Bayda Court of Appeal (Libya) on January 27th, 2021.

^{xxiv} Available at: <<https://www.dw.com/en/eastmed-gas-paving-the-way-for-a-new-geopolitical-era/a-49330250>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxv} Available at: <<https://apnews.com/article/turkey-libya-egypt-cairo-middle-east-fc1754ebee8429afd79a4750d6adaa40>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxvi} Roughly equivalent to the supply capacity of 30 thousand barrels per day.

^{xxvii} Available at: <<https://www.jpost.com/business-and-innovation/energy-and-infrastructure/article-721662>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxviii} Available at: <<https://en.globes.co.il/en/article-energean-ceo-were-looking-at-new-drilling-near-tamar-1001416136>>. Accessed December 2022.

^{xxix} Available at: <<https://corporatetwatch.org/energean-israeli-backed-greek-oil-company-hungry-for-mediterranean-gas/>>. Accessed December 2022.